

Report on integration of datasets and models

Deliverable 5.1

30th June 2025

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Title	Report on integration of datasets and models
Lead Beneficiary	University of Szczecin
Lead Author(s)	Paweł Terefenko (University of Szczecin), Jakub Śledziowski (University of Szczecin)
Contributors	Anaïs Couasnon (DELTA RES), Dominik Paprotny (PIK), Matthias Mengel (PIK), Daniel Cotterill (Met Office), Rachel Perks (Met Office), Martha Vogel (IRC RCCCCD), Andrzej Giza (University of Szczecin)
Deliverable number	5.1
Work Package	WP5
Submission date	30/06/2025

Dissemination Level

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online)	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	EU classified — Restreint-UE/EU-Restricted, Confidential-UE/EU-Confidential, Secret-UE/EU-Secret under Decision 2015/444	

Version History

Date	Version	Contributors	Comments
30.05.2025	0.1	Paweł Terefenko, Jakub Śledziowski, Dominik Paprotny	First version for internal review
19.06.2025	0.2	Inga Sauer	Internal review
23.06.3035	1.0	Paweł Terefenko, Jakub Śledziowski, Dominik Paprotny	Final review and first finished version

Citation

Terefenko, P. and Śledziowski, J. (2025): Report on integration of datasets and models. Horizon Europe project COMPASS. Deliverable D5.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15517565

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Funded by the
European Union

The COMPASS project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135481

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority HADEA can be held responsible for them.

Executive summary

Deliverable D5.1 presents a modular and scalable workflow framework designed to support the impact attribution of climate-related compound events. Developed within the COMPASS project, the workflow will be demonstrated using UC5 (Poland – heatwaves and droughts), and conceptually extended to other use cases (UC1–UC4). This provides a foundation for generalising the approach while also acknowledging its current practical scope and limitations. It shows how to integrate publicly available datasets and open-source modelling tools into a unified, script-based environment for generating both factual and counterfactual climate scenarios.

The proposed solution is not limited to a specific case study or hazard type. Instead, it offers a flexible foundation that can be adapted to diverse geographical contexts and climate risks, including but not limited to heatwaves, droughts, floods, tropical cyclones, and winter storms. It does so by leveraging:

- global climate datasets (e.g. ERA5, ERA5-Land),
- regional high-resolution observations (e.g. EMO-1),
- and impact and statistical models (e.g. ISIMIP3BASD, LISVAP, ATTRICI, CatBoost),

enabling consistent integration of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability data for comprehensive attribution assessments (Fig 1.).

Fig. 1. Scalable workflow architecture for climate attribution, allowing hazard- and region-specific configuration based on open data and models.

The framework supports both probabilistic (unconditioned) and storyline (conditioned) attribution approaches, making it suitable for a wide range of scientific and policy-relevant applications. Its open and modular design ensures reproducibility, transparency, and ease of use for researchers, decision-makers, and other stakeholders engaged in climate risk assessment.

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Ultimately, this deliverable provides a conceptual and operational foundation for integrating climate and impact datasets through a transferable workflow architecture. Beyond its standalone value, the conceptual workflow presented in D5.1 (Report on integration of datasets and models) serves as the technical basis for follow-up deliverables—particularly D4.5 (Prototype of the operational use case), which focuses on the application of attribution results, D5.2 (Online web-based demonstrator) with presentation of workflow implementation in different use cases and D5.3 (Open-source software development), which documents continued development, refinement, and scaling of the system.

At the same time, the development of an automated event attribution workflow also revealed several key challenges. These include ensuring the robustness of attribution results across diverse data sources, managing the computational demands of high-resolution modeling, and harmonizing heterogeneous datasets across use cases. Lessons learned from each use case have been instrumental in identifying these barriers and proposing pragmatic solutions.

The developed approach contributes to the overarching goals of climate resilience, knowledge-based adaptation strategies, and improved understanding of the human influence on extreme weather and climate events.

To summarize, the presented COMPASS workflow for climate and impact attribution is:

- **Modular and open-source:** The workflow is composed of interoperable components that can be tailored to different hazards, regions, and impact models, using only open-source tools and datasets.
- **Globally applicable:** The workflow is demonstrated for heatwaves and droughts in Poland (UC5). However, the proposed workflow architecture is scalable to other hazards (e.g. floods, storms) and locations, including the full range of COMPASS use cases.
- **Supporting both factual and counterfactual scenarios:** Through integration with the ATTRICI model, the workflow enables comparative attribution to isolate the influence of climate change on extreme events.
- **Towards operational implementation and integration:** Scaling the workflow requires activities such as calibration, validation, incorporation of local data, and expert judgement on model configuration—steps that currently cannot be fully automated and different challenges are faced depending on the characteristics of the compound extreme. However, the workflow is already being implemented in an operational demonstrator for UC5 (heatwaves and droughts in Poland), supporting its future integration into regional climate services, adaptation assessments, and decision-support platforms.
- **Designed for co-development:** The workflow is built to evolve with stakeholder needs, the architecture encourages collaboration across research, policy, and practice communities.

Table of Contents

- Executive summary 4
- 1. Introduction..... 7
- 2. Conceptual Framework..... 8
- 3. Workflow Design 10
 - 3.1 Hazard Layer (L1)..... 12
 - 3.2 Climate Data Layer (L2) 13
 - 3.3 Integration Layer (L3)..... 15
 - 3.3.1 Bias adjustment and downscaling 16
 - 3.3.2 Counterfactuals 16
 - 3.3.3. Hazard modelling..... 17
 - 3.4 Impact Layer (L4) 18
 - 3.5 Attribution Outcome Layer (L5)..... 20
- 4. Workflow implementation summary 22
- 5. Conclusions 23
- Annex 1: Input Dataset Reference Table 25
- Annex 2: Use Cases workflow implementation 26
 - UC1 – Extra-tropical cyclone Xynthia – France 2010..... 26
 - UC2a – Winter storms 2013/2014..... 26
 - UC2b – Summer heatwave 2022..... 26
 - UC3 – Tropical cyclones in Eastern Africa..... 27
 - UC4 – Tropical cyclone Eta and Iota in Honduras 27
 - UC5 – Heatwaves and Droughts in Poland 27
- References 29

1. Introduction

The increasing frequency, intensity, and complexity of climate-related extreme events poses significant challenges for risk assessments and decision-making. Understanding the role of climate change in driving these events and their impacts on human and natural systems requires robust, scalable frameworks for event attribution that combine multiple data sources and modelling approaches.

Deliverable D5.1, developed within Work Package 5 of the COMPASS project, contributes to this effort by presenting a flexible workflow architecture for the integration of climate and impact datasets. The workflow was initially developed and will be demonstrated in Use Case 5 (Poland – heatwaves and droughts), which served as a testing ground for the entire chain from data to impacts. Building on this foundation, the conceptual framework is then evaluated for its potential applicability and adaptability to other use cases (UC1–UC4) involving different climate hazards and geographies. This workflow supports both factual and counterfactual analyses, enabling attribution studies across various spatial scales, hazard types, and impact domains.

Rather than providing a one-off technical solution, this deliverable outlines a conceptual framework and a perspective on its potential operationalisation for the different use cases. Recognising the challenge of developing a single, fully automated solution for all event types and regions, the workflow is intentionally designed as a modular and adaptable system. While automation is maximised, expert judgement remains essential at key decision points, such as hazard definition, threshold selection, and interpretation of results.

Automation in this context currently applies to selected components of the attribution workflow, primarily the processing of climate data through the ATTRICI model. This enables automated generation of counterfactual climate datasets based on user-defined configuration files. Changing the region or data range requires editing the configuration script. While the broader workflow is modular and scriptable, additional components (e.g., hazard modelling or impact estimation) may still require manual adjustment or expert supervision depending on the region and use case.

The workflow distinguishes three attribution drivers: a) long-term climatic trends, b) anthropogenic forcing (emissions), and c) socio-economic changes in exposure and vulnerability. In the current implementation, only trend-removal (ATTRICI) is fully integrated and automated. Other methods – such as HadGEM3-A, SMILEs and SSP-based socio-economic counterfactuals – are conceptually supported by the workflow architecture but require additional setup.

The proposed architecture builds on publicly available climate and impact datasets, with a particular focus on the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), including products such as ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2023) and ERA5-Land (Balsamo et al., 2009; Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). It also integrates other EU-enabled datasets, such as - EMO-1 (European Meteorological Observations (Gomes et al., 2020; Musil et al., 2022) provided by the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS). A detailed list of the datasets available to be used in the workflow is provided in Annex 1.

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

The framework incorporates open-source tools for bias adjustment, downscaling, different hazard detection and open-source scripting languages (e.g. Python, Bash) and interactive development environments (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks), ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and ease of adaptation.

The attribution framework is designed to support a broad range of compound hazards — including droughts, floods, tropical cyclones, and heatwaves —and to accommodate different attribution methods. These include both probabilistic approaches (described in D2.1), which quantify changes in event likelihood or intensity, and storyline-based framings, which analyse specific event trajectories under observed or modified conditions. While this deliverable presents a generic, conceptual workflow, its structure is grounded in practical implementation. Specifically, the workflow architecture has been developed and tested through the lens of Use Case 5 (UC5)— focusing on drought and heatwave attribution in Poland. The UC5 example informs the modular structure of the framework, which is then assessed for potential reuse and transferability across other COMPASS use cases (UC1–UC4).

This report provides a high-level description of the attribution workflow components, logic, and potential applications. It is intended as both a conceptual guide and a foundation for further implementation, integration, and co-development across the research, policy, and operationalisation communities. Use cases developed within the project (WP4 and WP5), and the technical work packages on hazard, exposure and vulnerability (WP1, WP2 and WP3), have informed the structure and logic of this workflow.

2. Conceptual Framework

This framework follows a three-pillar logic consistent with international best practices in climate risk analysis:

1. **Hazard:** the physical characteristics of extreme climate events (e.g. temperature, precipitation, wind, surge).
2. **Exposure:** the location, distribution, and value of assets or systems affected by the hazard.
3. **Vulnerability:** the sensitivity or resilience of those exposed systems to climatic stressors.

Rather than prescribing a fixed model or region, the workflow provides a template that users can adapt to different questions, data availabilities, and contexts. It is built from modular components—data inputs, pre-processing scripts, modelling modules—which can be tailored to various hazards and geographies.

Key Workflow Objectives:

- **Hazard–Exposure–Vulnerability (HEV) as key components of risk:** The framework is structured around the core elements of risk—hazard, exposure, and vulnerability—integrating physical, spatial, and social factors that influence impact. Hazard layers are built using climate indicators computed from datasets such as ERA5, ERA5-Land, and CMIP6, with methodological support from Deliverables 1.1 and 2.1. Exposure layers are based on the global HANZE dataset and the gridded data from Deliverable 3.1 - Exposure

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

datasets at multiple scales (e.g. population, GDP, and asset values across SSP scenarios), while vulnerability aspects are informed by models developed in Deliverable 3.3 - Vulnerability models for multiple hazards.

- **Automated, data-driven attribution with support for storylines scenarios:** The workflow supports automated climate attribution by leveraging structured comparisons between factual and counterfactual climate data. This data-driven approach enables robust, repeatable assessments of changes in hazard characteristics and associated impacts. While the workflow is primarily designed for automated analyses, its modularity also allows users to define and explore storyline-like scenarios by conditioning the inputs (e.g. selecting specific events, or changes in boundary conditions), thus enabling hybrid applications across scientific and planning contexts.
- **Modularity, scalability and adaptability:** Each component of the workflow (data ingestion, pre-processing, modelling, output analysis) is modular and script based. The architecture can be easily reconfigured to accommodate different climate hazards (e.g. droughts, floods, cyclones), geographical scales (local, national, regional), and data sources (e.g. reanalyses, station data, ensembles). The design is scalable across spatial and temporal domains.
- **Counterfactual capability with societal impact framing:** The workflow supports climate impact attribution by comparing impacts under observed (factual) and synthetic (counterfactual) climate conditions. Climate counterfactual datasets are generated using the ATTRICI method (Mengel et al., 2021), which constructs a physically consistent detrended version of observed climate data by removing long-term changes correlated with global mean temperature. This enables attribution of observed impacts specifically to long-term climate trends. In addition, the workflow accommodates scenario-driven assessments of exposure and vulnerability by integrating alternative socio-economic datasets (e.g. HANZE, SSP-based projections). While not counterfactuals in the strict climate sense, these alternative scenarios allow analysts to explore how different distributions of population, land use, or asset value might influence impact outcomes. The modular structure also enables conditional scenario exploration based on specific climate drivers or patterns (e.g. SST anomalies, blocking regimes), facilitating storyline-based framing even without formal storyline models. This design supports flexible, risk-informed, and forward-looking impact assessments across multiple dimensions of change.
- **Transferability through global data and tools:** The workflow's reliance on globally available datasets (e.g. ERA5, CMIP6, HANZE, EMO-1) and open-source models designed for global applications ensures high transferability. Minimal configuration changes allow the same architecture to be used for different event types (e.g. droughts, tropical cyclones, compound floods) and regions (e.g. Mozambique, France, United Kingdom).

3. Workflow Design

The workflow developed in this deliverable is designed as a modular, script-based architecture that can be easily configured, extended, or replicated across different climate hazards and regions. Its primary aim is to support event attribution studies through a flexible sequence of data integration, transformation, and modelling steps. The design philosophy is focusing on interoperability, reproducibility, and ease of adaptation.

Rather than prescribing a single pipeline, the workflow implements several scalability solutions and is composed of independent, functional blocks that can be connected or substituted depending on the needs of the analysis. This modularity enables users to adjust:

- the **geographical area** (e.g. Europe, country, region, catchments, etc.),
- the **hazard type** (e.g. heatwaves, droughts, floods, storms),
- the **data sources** (e.g. ERA5, national datasets),
- or the **modelling approach** (e.g. statistical downscaling vs. dynamical, impact models vs. exposure overlays).

The workflow consists of five main layers:

- 1) Hazard Layer**, where area, natural hazard and its indicators are defined ;
- 2) Climate Data Layer**, where relevant datasets and variables are queried;
- 3) Integration Layer**, where factual and counterfactual hazard data are calculated;
- 4) Impact Layer**, where hazard is combined with exposure and vulnerability;
- 5) Attribution Outcome Layer**, where probabilistic and storyline impact attribution is presented, including validation of impact model outputs.

The entire workflow is implemented using open scripting environments (Python, Bash, Jupyter Notebooks), and structured in a way that facilitates both step-by-step execution and automated batch processing. A schematic overview of the architecture is provided in Fig. 2 and description of its implementation in Use Cases in Annex 2.

By organising the system in layers, the workflow provides users with a robust yet adaptable foundation for implementing climate attribution analyses across disciplines, hazards, and scales.

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Fig. 2. Modular attribution workflow architecture.

The five use cases (UC) developed under WP4 and WP5 of the COMPASS project serve as demonstrators for how the workflow can be configured and applied in practice. These use cases include:

Table 1. Overview of the considered Use Cases (UC) for Phase I of the COMPASS project

UC no.	Major hazard types considered	Event name and date	Region	Dominant innovation for the impact attribution framework	Partner Lead partner indicated in bold
1	- Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge) - Windstorm	Extra-tropical cyclone Xynthia (2010)	France	Multi-scale exposure and multivariate vulnerability	PIK , MO, DELT
2a	- Wind - Pluvial flooding - Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge)	Winter Storms 2013/2014	United Kingdom	Attribution method	MO , PIK, DELT
2b	- Heatwave - Drought -	Summer Heatwave 2022	United Kingdom	Attribution method	MO
3a	- Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge, waves) - Wind - Pluvial flooding - River flooding	Tropical cyclone Idai (2019), Kenneth (2019) and Freddy (2023)	Mozambique	Hazard	DELT , MO, PIK, IRC RCCCCD
3b	- Drought - Saltwater intrusion	2015/2016	Mozambique	Hazard	DELT , MO, PIK, IRC RCCCCD
4	- Pluvial flooding - River flooding - Coastal flooding (storm surge)	Tropical cyclone Eta and Iota (2020)	Caribbean	Vulnerability	IRC RCCCCD , DELT, PIK
5	- Heatwave	No specific event	Poland	Operationalisation	US , PIK

	- Drought				
--	-----------	--	--	--	--

3.1 Hazard Layer (L1)

The workflow can be applied to various types of compound hazards at various spatial domains, demonstrating its adaptability through parameter reconfiguration and modular model selection following the guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates (Aleksandrova et al. 2024). In this layer, the term Hazard Layer refers to the definition of the event type, spatial extent, and relevant thresholds or indicators used in the attribution analysis. It does not perform hazard modelling per se—that is handled in the Integration Layer. This layer serves as a scoping and setup phase that feeds the subsequent steps with hazard-specific parameters and datasets.

Thematic flexibility includes:

- Switching between different hazards by adapting the hazard module;
- Adjusting event definitions or thresholds based on user framing.

Spatial scalability examples:

- National-level attribution (e.g. UC5 – Poland),
- Sub-regional analysis (e.g. UC1 – coastal France),
- Continental/global framing using ensemble datasets (e.g. SMILEs in UC2 or CMIP6 in UC4).

In practical application to UC5, Python scripts in each further module will be prepared with flexible parameters for spatial boundaries, variables, and resolution based on the hazards and spatial scale chosen. This enables rapid scaling and thematic redirection without major structural modifications to the workflow.

The modular design of the hazard layer means that:

- necessary datasets (e.g. from national meteorological offices or Copernicus services) are defined in this layer which allows users to incorporate them later with minimal effort,
- users can substitute variables depending on hazard type,
- custom regions of interest can be defined at runtime, enabling scalable analyses.

Scripts developed in UC5 will include flexible configuration options for region, resolution, variable selection, and time range, making them suitable for both batch processing and exploratory analysis.

Table 2. Implementation of hazard module layer (L1) in the Use Cases

Use Case (UC)	Implementation
UC1 France	ERA5 reanalysis data at 0.25-degree resolution (1950-2024) for European coastal waters (sea level pressure, u- and v-component wind speed for storm surge simulation) or France (wind speed for windstorm impact)

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

		simulation). For sea level calculation, 0.5-degree significant wave height from ERA5 are also included. Long-term sea level and tides from other datasets. Additional hindcast climate data from HadGEM3-A-N216 at about 1-degree resolution (wind speed for 2006-2013, 15 ensemble members).
UC2a	United Kingdom	Type of hazard: compound flooding, where the key drivers considered are rainfall leading to high river discharge, and elevated coastal water levels (storm surge, waves and tides), Spatial Scale: Somerset, southern England, Dynamic downscaling is used, i.e. through a series of physically-based models (i.e. hydrological model for the discharge, coastal hydrodynamic model for the coastal water levels).
UC2b	United Kingdom	Type of hazard: compound drought and heatwave, Spatial Scale: southern England, Extreme event definition for drought and heatwave.
UC3	Mozambique	The hazard driver variables for tropical cyclone induced flooding considered are rainfall, coastal water levels (tides storm surge, and waves) and river discharge. Dynamic downscaling is used, i.e. through a series of physically-based models (i.e. hydrological model for the discharge, coastal hydrodynamic model for the coastal water levels) and a parametric model for the tropical cyclone wind fields.
UC4	Honduras	Type of hazard: Pluvial flooding, river flooding, coastal flooding (storm surge) Spatial scale: Honduras, Dynamic downscaling is used, i.e. through a series of physically-based models (hydrological model for the discharge, coastal hydrodynamic model for the coastal water levels) and a parametric model for the tropical cyclone wind profiles.
UC5	Poland	Type of hazard: compound drought and heatwave; Spatial scale: Poland; Extreme event definitions for heatwaves and droughts (selection of substitute variables depending on hazard).

3.2 Climate Data Layer (L2)

This layer includes scripts for downloading raw data from various climate sources. The scalability solution will enable adjusting the geographical extension of downloaded dataset based on spatial scale defined in the hazard layer (L1). Further, the tools will support additional processes such as reformatting and aggregating raw data from various climate sources. It handles:

- conversion of file formats (e.g. GRIB to NetCDF),

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

- temporal harmonisation (e.g. hourly to daily),
- spatial subsetting and masking,
- merging of reanalysis and observational datasets.

The Data Layer is agnostic to specific datasets, but typically includes datasets such as:

- **Global reanalyses** (e.g. ERA5, ERA5-Land): used as the primary source for continuous climate fields, especially temperature, precipitation, radiation, and wind.
- **Regional high-resolution data** (e.g. EMO-1): used for downscaling and validation, offering finer spatial detail based on station observations.
- **Ensemble simulations** (e.g. CMIP, SMILEs): supporting counterfactual analyses and uncertainty assessment.
- **Marine and coastal products** (e.g. sea surface height, wave height, ocean currents from CMEMS, tides and storm surges from CDS Copernicus (Muis et al, 2022)): providing essential inputs for coastal and ocean-related hazards, such as storm surge, wave impact, and tropical cyclone analysis.
- **Hazard-specific products** (e.g. GloFAS, IBTrACS): used when the event type requires specialised inputs beyond general climate variables.

A full list of climate dataset categories for attribution studies has been presented in the deliverable 1.1 Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates (Aleksandrova et al. 2024).

Table 3. Implementation of data acquisition layer (L2) in UCs

Use Case	Implementation
UC1 France	ERA5 reanalysis data obtained via Copernicus API. Additional hindcast climate data from Met Office obtained via FTP.
UC2a United Kingdom	CEH-GEAR data of 1km gridded estimates of hourly rainfall for Great Britain for the period 1990-2016 downloaded from the online catalogue (Lewis et al. 2022); ERA5 reanalysis data obtained via Copernicus API; Dataset of global sea level related variables including tides, storm surges and sea level rise from 1950 to 2050 Muis et al. 2022); Historical flood map for England, accessed from Defra Data Services Platform and used for model validation.
UC2b United Kingdom	HadUKGrid data of gridded climate variables (precipitation and temperature) derived from the network of UK land surface observations, downloaded from CEDA (Met Office, 2018); ERA5 (temperature) reanalysis data obtained via Copernicus API; Vaisala observational data of surface temperature (10-minute data extending from 2001 to 2025).

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

UC3 Mozambique	ERA5 and ERA5-Land for the tropical cyclone event duration and up to one year before for the hydrological model: reanalysis of key climate variables downloaded automatically via API; IBTrACS: records of historical tropical cyclones, including their tracks and various key meteorological indicator such as wind speed (object-based) The OSMnx python package is used to automatically download the OSM data (Boeing, 2017).
UC4 Honduras	ERA5 and ERA5-Land for the tropical cyclone event duration and up to one year before for the hydrological model: reanalysis of key climate variables downloaded automatically via API; IBTrACS: records of historical tropical cyclones, including their tracks and various key meteorological indicators such as wind speed (object-based). OSM building footprint data downloaded through OSMnx tool.
UC5 Poland	ERA5 and ERA5-Land (1950–2024): reanalysis of key climate variables downloaded automatically via API; EMO-1 (1990–2022): high-resolution gridded observations for downscaling; Crop yield statistics: national datasets (e.g. GUS) used for model validation.

3.3 Integration Layer (L3)

The Integration Layer serves as the central interface for harmonising and preparing climate datasets prior to their use in attribution analyses. It is designed to ensure that heterogeneous data sources—differing in spatial resolution, temporal frequency, format, or origin—can be standardised and made interoperable with the rest of the workflow.

This layer connects global climate datasets (e.g. ERA5, ERA5-Land, CMIP6), regional observations (e.g. EMO-1, national stations), and hazard-specific inputs (e.g. GloFAS for river discharges, IBTrACS for tropical cyclones) to a common processing pipeline. This allows researchers to use consistent, bias-corrected, and spatially matched data regardless of the event type or study region. Calculating event-relevant indices such as potential evapotranspiration (e.g. via LISVAP (Balance and Model, 2008; Van Der Knijff et al., 2010)), monthly means, seasonal maxima or minima, temperature thresholds, or water balance indicators. These metrics serve as the basis for further hazard and impact quantification.

By standardising inputs from multiple data sources, the Integration Layer ensures that climate attribution studies are based on high-quality, harmonised datasets. This enhances the credibility of the workflow's outputs and enables meaningful comparisons across hazard types, regions, and time periods.

3.3.1 Bias adjustment and downscaling

The modularity of this step allows users to apply alternative bias adjustment or downscaling techniques if needed, such as quantile-based methods or statistical models trained to reproduce high-resolution climate patterns.

Each dataset may have different file formats, calendar conventions, coordinate systems, or metadata standards. The integration layer is responsible for ensuring that all datasets:

- are projected to the same spatial grid and coordinate reference system,
- are resampled or aggregated to consistent temporal resolutions,
- have harmonised dimensions (e.g. time, lat, lon) and variable names,
- are free of format-specific inconsistencies (e.g. missing metadata, non-standard calendars).

As input datasets often differ in magnitude or distribution, bias adjustment methods are applied to align modelled or reanalysis data with high-quality observational benchmarks. The integration layer supports:

- Quantile-based **bias correction** (e.g. ISIMIP3BASD (Lange, 2019)),
- **Simple scaling** or delta change approaches, when observation data is limited,
- **Custom workflows**, where local data is integrated for statistical calibration.

The goal is to ensure that all data entering the impact models are as consistent, comparable, and interpretable as possible, preserving physical meaning while correcting for known biases.

3.3.2 Counterfactuals

One of the key functionalities of the workflow is the ability to compare model outputs under observed (factual) and synthetic (counterfactual) climate conditions. This capability enables the analysis of the influence of climate trends on impact metrics, while controlling for internal climate variability.

In the designed implementation, the automated workflow includes procedures for generating counterfactual climate datasets using the ATTRICI model (Mengel et al., 2021). ATTRICI removes the long-term trend from historical climate observations (e.g., ERA5), producing physically consistent counterfactual time series that preserve internal variability but exclude the effects of long-term warming. This method enables attribution to historical climate change, without requiring explicit model-based emissions scenarios.

Although the default version of the workflow focuses on ATTRICI, the architecture is designed to be extensible. It can accommodate additional counterfactual approaches such as:

- Paired ensemble simulations (e.g., CMIP6), for attribution to anthropogenic forcings;
- Large initial condition ensembles (e.g., SMILES), for probabilistic framing of event likelihood;
- Socio-economic counterfactuals, based on alternative exposure or vulnerability scenarios (e.g., different SSPs or historical configurations).

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

These approaches are not default defined in the automated pipeline, but they remain conceptually compatible with the modular integration layer described in this report.

3.3.3. Hazard modelling

This optional step is valid in cases where meteorological indicators (e.g. extreme temperature or wind speed) are not sufficient to represent the hazard. It can involve:

- Calculation of hydrological indicators (e.g. evapotranspiration)
- Hydrological modelling (river flows)
- Hydrodynamic modelling (storm surges, flood inundation zones)

Table 4. Implementation of integration layer (L3) in UCs

UC	Implementation
UC1 France	<p>Downscaling not used due to lack of methods suitable for downscaling hourly data and general sufficiency of ERA5 or ERA5-Land data for hydrodynamic modelling of storm surge and wind damage modelling. Also, no observational data enables downscaling over maritime areas. The HadGEM3-A-N216 data was interpolated to fit the grid of ERA5.</p> <p>For coastal impact modelling, storm surge was calculated from ERA5 wind and air pressure data using Delft3D model implemented by Paprotny et al. (2024)</p> <p>Transformed-stationary Extreme Value Analysis used to derive counterfactual wind, storm surge and wave height. Long-term sea level datasets were used to remove the effect of SLR from extreme surge level. Alternative counterfactual approach for wind used with HadGEM3-A-N216 providing simulations with and without anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions.</p>
UC2a United Kingdom	<p>Climate counterfactuals are used for season-long (DJF) precipitation and mean sea level component of the extreme water levels for a probabilistic attribution approach.</p>
UC2b United Kingdom	<p>The HadUKGrid data is downscaled using the Vaisala observational data to capture local temperature characteristics for impact modelling.</p> <p>Climate counterfactuals conditioned on SSTs for the year of the event, are used specifically for a bivariate attribution analysis of the 9-month (DJFMAMJJA) effective rainfall and the high summer temperatures (JJA).</p>
UC3 Mozambique	<p>Data harmonization (coordinate reference system, time, lat, lon, variable names, etc.).</p> <p>Dynamical downscaling is used to obtain tropical cyclone hazard variables. No further statistical downscaling is done.</p> <p>Climate counterfactuals created using a storyline approach by modifying separate climate drivers (rainfall, wind, sea level rise) following current approaches done for tropical cyclones storylines.</p>

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

UC4 Honduras	Data harmonization (coordinate reference system, time, lat, lon, variable names, etc.). Climate counterfactuals created using a storyline approach by modifying separate climate drivers (rainfall intensity) to historical conditions without climate signal and removing the first tropical cyclone Eta.
UC5 Poland	Data harmonization (coordinate reference system, time, lat, lon, variable names, etc.) BASD used to downscale ERA5-Land to 1' resolution with EMO-1, in order to produce meteorological data with adequate resolution for crop modelling. ATTRICI for counterfactual climate dataset generation. LISVAP to generate evapotranspiration data for crop impact modelling

3.4 Impact Layer (L4)

The Model Layer forms the analytical core of the event attribution workflow. It hosts all processes that transform hazard data into impacts. This includes detecting events, generating exposure overlays, and running impact models. These steps enable quantification how extreme events translate into physical damage, system responses, or societal outcomes.

The Impact Modelling layer is designed to be **modular and extensible**. It accommodates a wide variety of modelling approaches—including hydrological, agricultural, machine learning, and statistical methods—depending on the selected hazard and available data.

This layer includes several analytical components, which can be combined or adapted depending on the type of event and impact being assessed. Typical steps include:

- Exposure mapping and overlays: Integrating gridded exposure datasets, such as the HANZE database (Paprotny et al, 2023) and gridded GDP/population layers from Deliverable 3.1 (Paprotny 2025), to assess the spatial extent and scale of exposed assets or population. Exposure can be adjusted to the analysis scale and context.
- Vulnerability assumptions – static or scenario-based (if available), used to translate exposure into potential loss. Different vulnerability models can be implemented such as CatBoost machine learning model (Dorogush et al., 2018) for crop yield in UC5. Major vulnerability models for multiple hazards will be developed in COMPASS and presented in deliverable D3.3 planned for month 30 of the project.
- Impact modelling: Identifying extreme or compound events (e.g. droughts, heatwaves, compound floods) based on pre-defined or dynamically computed thresholds. The default method is a peak-over-threshold (POT) approach implemented for compound droughts and heatwaves in UC5 (Afroz et al, 202), though other classification schemes (e.g. percentile-based, SPI, or tailored algorithms) may be applied depending on the hazard type. Applying empirical or machine learning models to estimate quantitative impacts on

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

systems such as agriculture, health, or infrastructure. Risk can also be quantified using damage functions or vulnerability profiles layered with exposure and hazard inputs.

Where available, counterfactual vulnerability assumptions—such as alternative development pathways or historical vulnerability baselines—can also be applied, depending on the specific hazard and geographical context.

The Impact Layer is modular and supports substitution or extension depending on the hazard or sectoral context. The layer is not limited to any specific hazard or sector. **Users can expand the workflow** by:

- replacing or adding new impact models (e.g. heat stress indices, insurance loss models),
- adjusting input variables,
- linking the output to risk analysis frameworks or early warning systems.

Because the entire model layer is built from open-source tools, it can be adapted to suit different computational environments and research questions. Scripts can be executed independently or in pipeline mode using workflow managers.

Through its extensible and scenario-aware design, the impact layer supports interdisciplinary applications and policy-relevant climate attribution studies, from sectoral impact assessments to compound hazard analysis.

Each subcomponent of this layer—from indicator computation to event detection and impact modelling—can be independently customised or replaced, depending on the needs of the analysis.

Table 5. Implementation of impact modelling layer (L4) in UCs.

UC	Implementation
UC1 France	HANZE attribution model (Paprotny et al. 2025) was used to derive factual (2010) and counterfactual (1950) impacts for coastal flooding, including effects of (1) catchment alteration (2) exposure growth (3) exposure spatial distribution and economic structure change, (4) flood protection levels (5) flood vulnerability (relative loss). Three types of impacts are attributed: fatalities, population affected, and economic loss. Gridded fixed asset value from COMPASS D3.1 dataset (Paprotny, 2025) was used to derive factual (2010) and counterfactual (1850, 1950) impacts (economic loss only) from high wind speeds.
UC2a United Kingdom	Maximum flood depth data from the compound flooding model SFINCS is overlaid with building footprints from OpenStreetMap (OSM) (Copyright and License OpenStreetMap, n.d.) or where appropriate national level data.
UC2b United Kingdom	Computation of climate indicators (monthly means, seasonal maxima, and temperature thresholds);

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

	Regression relationship between runway surface temperature and air temperature; Event detection based on climate data with peak-over-threshold methodology; Civil Aviation Authority data on UK airport usage, specifically flight and passenger numbers.
UC3 Mozambique	The fast impact assessment tool Delft-FIAT (Wagenaar et al., 2017) is used to calculate the flood impact, i.e. flood damage from the tropical cyclones. Maximum flood depth data from the compound flooding model SFINCS is overlaid with building footprints from OpenStreetMap (OSM) (Copyright and License OpenStreetMap, n.d.). The damage is expressed in US Dollars, using depth-damage curves for flooding and maximum potential damage per building type from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) (Moel et al., 2016).
UC4 Honduras	Following the same approach from UC3, the Delft-FIAT (Wagenaar et al., 2017) is used to calculate the flood impact, i.e. flood damage from the tropical cyclones Eta and Ioata. Maximum flood depth data from the compound flooding model SFINCS is overlaid with building footprints from OpenStreetMap (OSM) (Copyright and License OpenStreetMap, n.d.).
UC5 Poland	Computation of climate indicators (monthly means, seasonal maxima or minima, temperature thresholds, etc.); LISVAP for reference evapotranspiration (ET _o) computation; Event detection based on climate data with peak-over-threshold methodology; CatBoost machine learning model.

3.5 Attribution Outcome Layer (L5)

Attribution outcome layer supports both probabilistic attribution and scenario-based storytelling, depending on the chosen framing. The same approach can be extended to counterfactual exposure and vulnerability data if available for a given region or sector. Modelled factual impacts are aggregated and presented for different drivers and scenarios. Finally, comparison analysis of the factual and counterfactuals can be calculated both in absolute and relative terms.

Both factual and counterfactual datasets are processed through the same model chain, allowing for consistent comparison of:

- impact magnitude (e.g. crop yield, flood damage),
- event frequency and intensity,
- attribution metrics such as change in impact or attributable risk.

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Ensuring the quality, consistency, and transparency of input data, intermediate outputs, and final attribution results is a core objective of the workflow design. The whole system incorporates multiple layers of quality assurance and validation procedures to maintain scientific robustness and facilitate stakeholder trust. Quality assurance and validation gathered in the output layers concern all stages of the workflow and it starts with datasets —such as ERA5, ERA5-Land, CMEMS, EMO-1, GloFAS which undergo quality control procedures either during their production or during ingestion. These include:

- Verification of metadata (e.g. calendar encoding, coordinate systems),
- Standardisation of variable naming and dimensional structures,
- Detection of missing data, outliers, or physical inconsistencies,
- Validation against independent observational datasets (where available).

Reanalysis products (e.g. ERA5) integrate diverse observational sources via data assimilation, ensuring internal consistency and temporal continuity. Regional datasets (e.g. EMO-1) include quality-controlled station data subjected to interpolation using documented geostatistical methods.

At each processing step—from ingestion to downscaling and impact modelling—the workflow performs internal consistency checks to prevent propagation of errors. These include:

- Automated validation of NetCDF structure (e.g. time encoding, units, dimensions),
- Temporal completeness checks (e.g. continuous time series, no gaps),
- Spatial coherence diagnostics (e.g. matching grid extents),
- Unit and scale harmonisation between datasets.

Tools such as `cdo sinfo`, `ncdump`, and custom Python diagnostics are used throughout the processing chain to support runtime quality assurance and consistency checks.

Where applicable, models used in the workflow are validated against observed impact data or historical benchmarks. For example:

- Crop yield models are cross-validated using hold-out years and compared against national statistics,
- Hydrological components (e.g. LISVAP outputs) could be compared with known benchmarks,
- Counterfactual outputs from ATTRICI are assessed for statistical coherence with factual distributions (e.g. mean-preserving rank matching).

Additionally, users are encouraged to implement context-specific validation protocols depending on the modelled hazard and region.

Table 6. Implementation of attribution outcome layer (L5) in UCs.

UC	Implementation
UC1 France	Modelled factual impacts are aggregated and presented for different drivers and scenarios, including three different impacts of floods for 1950

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

		baseline, and two approaches to windstorm counterfactuals (1950 or pre-industrial baseline). A validation is made with insurance data on the magnitude and the spatial distribution of economic losses at regional scale (windstorm) or municipality scale (coastal flooding).
UC2a	United Kingdom	Climate counterfactual attribution using a probabilistic approach for season-long (DJF) precipitation and mean sea level component of the extreme water levels, to produce flood maps in factual and counterfactual climates that can be used to attribute impacts. Storyline counterfactuals of exposure (i.e. population/properties exposed) are used to attribute changes in exposure. A flood defense counterfactual (i.e. without flood defenses) is used for a storyline attribution analysis of changes in vulnerability/exposure.
UC2b	United Kingdom	Climate counterfactuals are used for both a conditional attribution analysis of the multivariate hazard (Drought-Heatwave) and attribution of impacts on an airport. Counterfactuals of exposure for the event is examined using airport usage/infrastructure in the past and future.
UC3	Mozambique	Climate attribution analysis using a storyline approach. A comparison of the factual and counterfactuals is calculated both in absolute and relative terms for the flood damages. The counterfactuals include changes in rainfall, wind (and thus storm surge) and sea-level rise, due to removing the climate change trend.
UC4	Honduras	Climate attribution analysis made using a storyline approach. A comparison of the factual and counterfactuals is done. The counterfactuals include change in rainfall intensity, remove the previous tropical cyclone Eta and non-climate counterfactuals such as location of shelters and health infrastructure.
UC5	Poland	Comparison of impacts of climate change taking into account factual and counterfactual changes. Quantification of the contribution of climate change to observed crop losses.

4. Workflow implementation summary

The core strength of the attribution workflow presented in this report lies in its scalability and adaptability. While the initial implementation has focused on droughts and heatwaves in Poland (UC5), the underlying structure is designed to support a broad range of hazards and geographic contexts.

While each use case focuses on specific hazards and datasets, they share a common analytical logic, demonstrating that the workflow is not a one-size-fits-all solution, but rather a versatile foundation for hazard-specific configuration. Therefore, the Use Cases demonstrate the

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

flexibility of the modular workflow across diverse hazards, framings, and geographic contexts. (Fig. 3).

Through its design, the workflow offers a bridge between scientific modelling and policy-relevant attribution, enabling consistent, scalable, and transparent analysis of climate-related events across domains and geographies.

Fig. 3. Modular attribution workflow implementation covered in realized Use Cases analysis.

5. Conclusions

The attribution workflow presented in this report offers a robust, modular, and scalable approach for integrating climate and impact data in support of event attribution studies. It has been designed with flexibility in mind, enabling users to analyse a wide range of hazards, apply diverse modelling approaches, and operate across geographic contexts—from local case studies to continental applications.

By combining global datasets (e.g. ERA5, CMEMS), high-resolution observational products (e.g. EMO-1), and open-source models (e.g. ISIMIP3BASD, ATTRICI, LISVAP), the workflow provides a strong technical foundation for climate impact analysis under both factual and counterfactual scenarios.

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Its design emphasises:

Modularity – users can adapt or replace components to suit specific data availability, hazards, or sectors;

Transparency – all processing steps are script-based, version-controlled, and documented;

Scalability – through parameterisation, the workflow can be deployed for any user-defined region or hazard type;

Policy relevance – by enabling robust attribution of event impacts, the workflow can inform risk management, adaptation planning, and loss and damage mechanisms.

Despite the progress made in designing a modular and scalable attribution framework, several important limitations remain before full operationalisation can be achieved. A key constraint is the availability and readiness of essential input datasets. For instance, datasets like IBTRACS, used for tropical cyclone analysis, may have temporal lags and incomplete coverage, limiting real-time or near-real-time attribution. Further, for many of the more complex hazard types, meteorological variables need to be translated into hazard maps using hydrological/hydrodynamic or other types of models. This requires not only the input data to be operational and of good quality but also automatization of the whole model chain in order to be applied at a regional scale with sufficient accuracy. For some specific event which faces data limitations, or which require model choices, manual steps may be inevitable. These issues highlight the need for ongoing collaboration with data providers and for robust fallback strategies to ensure continuity and reliability in operational settings.

In summary, the workflow bridges the gap between climate data, impact models, and policy applications. It is not a static product, but a living architecture designed to evolve with future data availability, scientific developments, and societal needs.

Annex 1: Input Dataset Reference Table

Dataset Name	Provider	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Variables	Format	Access Method
ERA5	ECMWF Copernicus CDS	31 km	Hourly	Temperature, precipitation, radiation, wind speed	NetCDF / GRIB	CDS API
ERA5-Land	ECMWF Copernicus CDS	9 km	Hourly	Same as ERA5, optimized for land	NetCDF	CDS API
CMIP6	ESGF (various institutions)	Varies (typically ~100 km)	Daily / Monthly	GCM output: temperature, precipitation, etc.	NetCDF	ESGF Nodes
SMILES	Various (ETH, NCAR, etc.)	Model-dependent	Daily / Monthly	Ensemble climate simulations	NetCDF	Institutional repositories
EMO-1	Copernicus Emergency Management Service	1.5 km	Daily / Sub-daily	Temperature (min/max), precipitation, wind, radiation, vapor pressure	NetCDF	JRC or EMS internal
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service	~5–25 km (product dependent)	Hourly / Daily	Sea level, wave height, currents, SST	NetCDF	CMEMS Portal
GloFAS	Copernicus EMS	0.1°	Daily	River discharge, streamflow forecasts	NetCDF / GRIB	Copernicus GloFAS portal
IBTrACS	NOAA	Point data (track-based)	6-hourly	Tropical cyclone tracks, intensity, pressure	CSV / NetCDF	NOAA NCEI portal

Annex 2: Use Cases workflow implementation

UC1 – Extra-tropical cyclone Xynthia – France 2010

- **UC Leader:** PIK
- **Contributors:** Met Office
- **Country / Region:** France
- **Hazard Type:** compound (co-occurring due to common source) windstorm and coastal flood
- **Framing:** Probabilistic event attribution (factual vs counterfactual scenarios)
- **Input Datasets:** ERA5, multiple sea-level datasets, HANZE exposure dataset, D3.1 exposure dataset
- **Models Applied:** Delft3D, HANZE attribution model
- **Outcome / Purpose:** Attribution of fatalities, persons affected and economic losses of coastal flooding, and economic losses of windstorm
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:** largely follows the workflow, with some steps omitted where not necessary (particularly downscaling).

UC2a – Winter storms 2013/2014

- **UC Leader:** Met Office
- **Contributors:** PIK, Deltares
- **Country / Region:** Somerset, southern England
- **Hazard Type:** Compound flooding
- **Framing:** Probabilistic event attribution (factual vs counterfactual scenarios)

- **Input Datasets:** CEH-GEAR ; ERA5 ; global sea level related variables including tides, storm surges and sea level rise; HadGEM3-A climate attribution runs
- **Models Applied:** Delft3D-FM for coastal water levels, wflow for river discharges, SFINCS for flood mapping

- **Outcome / Purpose:** Attribution of flood extents and population exposed and/or building impacts
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:** Follows the generic workflow, but uses multiple hazard models to dynamically downscale

UC2b – Summer heatwave 2022

- **UC Leader:** Met Office
- **Contributors:**
- **Country / Region:** Southern England
- **Hazard Type:** Drought and heatwave
- **Framing:** Conditional event attribution (factual vs counterfactual scenarios)

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

- **Input Datasets:** HadUKGrid data; ERA5; Vaisala observational data ; HadGEM3-A climate attribution runs.
- **Models Applied:** Statistical modelling (POT, linear regression)
- **Outcome / Purpose:** Attribution of heatwave impacts of airport infrastructure
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:**

UC3 – Tropical cyclones in Eastern Africa

- **UC Leader:** Deltares
- **Contributors:** Met Office, Potsdam Institute for Impact Research, Red Cross Climate Center, Seven
- **Country / Region:** Mozambique
- **Hazard Type:** Tropical cyclone induced flooding: rainfall, winds as well as coastal hazards (tides and storm surge)
- **Framing:** Storyline attribution
- **Input Datasets:** ERA5, ERA5-Land, IBTrACS
- **Models Applied:** Delft3D-FM for coastal water levels, wflow for river discharges, SFINCS for flood mapping
- **Outcome / Purpose:** Attribution of direct flood damages from tropical cyclones Idai, Kenneth and Freddy
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:** Follow the generic workflow, but no statistical downscaling module used and the use of multiple hazard models to dynamically downscale

UC4 – Tropical cyclone Eta and Iota in Honduras

- **UC Leader:** IRC RCCCCD
- **Contributors:** Deltares, Potsdam Institute for Impact Research
- **Country / Region:** Honduras
- **Hazard Type:** Tropical cyclone induced flooding
- **Framing:** Storyline attribution
- **Input Datasets:** ERA5, IBTrACS, GloFAS, UNOSAT
- **Models Applied:** wflow, SFINCS
- **Outcome / Purpose:** Attribution of flood damages, displacement and health impacts from subsequent tropical cyclones Eta and Iota.
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:** Follow the generic workflow, but no statistical downscaling module used and the use of multiple hazard models to dynamically downscale

UC5 – Heatwaves and Droughts in Poland

- **UC Leader:** US
- **Contributors:** DELT, PIK

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

- **Country / Region:** Poland (national scale)
- **Hazard Type:** Heatwaves and agricultural droughts (compound event)
- **Framing:** Probabilistic event attribution (factual vs counterfactual scenarios)
- **Input Datasets:**
 - **ERA5 and ERA5-Land** (1950–2024): reanalysis of key climate variables
 - **EMO-1** (1990–2022): high-resolution gridded observations for downscaling
 - **LISVAP forcing inputs:** derived from reanalysis and observational blend
 - **Crop yield statistics:** national datasets (e.g. GUS) used for model validation
- **Models Applied:**
 - **ISIMIP3BASD** for bias adjustment and statistical downscaling
 - **LISVAP** for reference evapotranspiration (ET₀) computation
 - **ATTRICI** for counterfactual climate dataset generation
 - **CatBoost** machine learning model for crop yield impact attribution
- **Outcome / Purpose:**
 - Quantification of the contribution of climate change to observed crop losses
 - Comparison of impacts between factual (historical) and counterfactual (noanthropogenic forcing or no climate change) climate conditions
 - Demonstration of full workflow integration from climate forcing to impact attribution
- **Workflow Adaptation Notes:**
 - Full sequence of 12 processing steps implemented and tested
 - Modular structure allows substitution of crop model or hazard type
 - Datasets and bounding box specific to Poland; region and period adjustable in configuration

References

Afroz M, Chen G and Anandhi A (2023) Drought- and heatwave-associated compound extremes: A review of hotspots, variables, parameters, drivers, impacts, and analysis frameworks. *Front. Earth Sci.* 10:914437. doi: 10.3389/feart.2022.914437

Aleksandrova, N., Vertegaal, D., Couasnon, A., Perks, R., Cotterill, D. Vogel, M., Jack, C., Paprotny, D., Terefenko, P., Śledziowski, J. (2024): Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates. Horizon Europe project COMPASS. Deliverable D1.1.

Aleksandrova, N., Vertegaal, D., Couasnon, A., Perks, R., Cotterill, D. Vogel, M., Jack, C., Paprotny, D., Terefenko, P., Śledziowski, J. (2024): Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates. Horizon Europe project COMPASS. Deliverable D1.1.

Balance LW, Model FS. LISVAP. JRC Scientific and Technical Reports 2008.

Balsamo G, Beljaars A, Scipal K, Viterbo P, van den Hurk B, Hirschi M, et al. A revised hydrology for the ECMWF model: Verification from field site to terrestrial water storage and impact in the Integrated Forecast System. *Journal of hydrometeorology* 2009; 10: 623-643.

Cotterill, D., Perks, R., & Stott, P. (2024). Report on dataset on best-available methods and climate datasets for climate attribution. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14732362>

Dorogush AV, Ershov V, Gulin A. CatBoost: gradient boosting with categorical features support. arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.11363 2018.

Gomes G, Thiemig V, Skøien JO, Ziese M, Rauthe-Schöch A, Rustemeier E, et al. EMO: A high-resolution multi-variable gridded meteorological data set for Europe. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) 2020.

Hersbach H, Bell B, Berrisford P, Biavati G, Horányi A, Muñoz Sabater J, et al. ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present, Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)[data set], 2023.

Lange S. Trend-preserving bias adjustment and statistical downscaling with ISIMIP3BASD (v1.0). *Geosci. Model Dev.* 2019; 12: 3055-3070.

Lewis, E.; Quinn, N.; Blenkinsop, S.; Fowler, H.J.; Freer, J.; Tanguy, M.; Hitt, O.; Coxon, G.; Bates, P.; Woods, R.; Fry, M.; Chevuturi, A.; Swain, O.; White, S.M. (2022). Gridded estimates of hourly areal rainfall for Great Britain 1990-2016 [CEH-GEAR1hr] v2. NERC EDS Environmental Information Data Centre. <https://doi.org/10.5285/fc9423d6-3d54-467f-bb2b-fc7357a3941f>

Mengel M, Treu S, Lange S, Frieler K. ATTRICI v1.1 – counterfactual climate for impact attribution. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 2021; 14: 5269-5284.

Met Office; Hollis, D.; McCarthy, M.; Kendon, M.; Legg, T.; Simpson, I. (2018): HadUK-Grid gridded and regional average climate observations for the UK. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, accessed 29-05-2024. <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/4dc8450d889a491ebb20e724debe2dfb>

Deliverable 5.1 – Report on integration of datasets and models

Muis S, Apecechea M.I, Álvarez J.A, Verlaan M, Yan K, Dullaart J, Aerts J, Duong T, Ranasinghe R, le Bars D, Haarsma R, Roberts M, (2022): Global sea level change time series from 1950 to 2050 derived from reanalysis and high resolution CMIP6 climate projections. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). DOI: 10.24381/cds.a6d42d60

Muñoz-Sabater J, Dutra E, Agustí-Panareda A, Albergel C, Arduini G, Balsamo G, et al. ERA5-Land: A state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications. *Earth system science data* 2021; 13: 4349-4383.

Musil T, Petrлік M, Saska M. SphereMap: Dynamic multi-layer graph structure for rapid safety-aware UAV planning. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 2022; 7: 11007-11014.

Paprotny D., Tilloy A., Treu S., Buch ., Vousdoukas, M. I., Feyen, L., Kreibich, H., Merz B., Frieler K., Mengel M. (2025) Attribution of flood impacts shows strong benefits of adaptation in Europe since 1950, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5430941/v1>

Paprotny, D. (2025). Exposure datasets at multiple scales [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14892500>

Paprotny, D. (2025). Exposure datasets at multiple scales [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14892500>

Paprotny, D., and Mengel, M. (2023) Population, land use and economic exposure estimates for Europe at 100 m resolution from 1870 to 2020. *Scientific Data*, 10, 372, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02282-0>

Paprotny, D., Mengel, M. Population, land use and economic exposure estimates for Europe at 100 m resolution from 1870 to 2020 (2023). *Scientific Data* 10, 372. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02282-0>

Paprotny, D., Rhein, B., Vousdoukas, M. I., Terefenko, P., Dottori, F., Treu, S., Śledziowski, J., Feyen, L., and Kreibich, H. (2024) Merging modelled and reported flood impacts in Europe in a combined flood event catalogue for 1950–2020, *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 28, 3983–4010, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-28-3983-2024>

Van Der Knijff J, Younis J, De Roo A. LISFLOOD: a GIS-based distributed model for river basin scale water balance and flood simulation. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science* 2010; 24: 189-212.